

Linguistic Landscape of Tourism Destinations in Gianyar, Bali

Sang Ayu Isnu Maharani¹, Ketut Artawa², Ida Ayu Made Puspani³, Ni Ketut Widya Purnawati⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Jalan Pulau Nias 13 Denpasar, Bali-Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research entitled "Linguistic Landscape of Tourism Destinations in Gianyar, Bali". This research was conducted with the aim of analyzing landscape dynamics in tourism destinations in Bali, specifically in Gianyar regency. It focuses to map or categorize LL dynamic and also analyzing the pattern construction of Linguistic Landscape (LL) found in those destinations. The method applied for this research is a non-participatory observation method, using image capture technique, note-taking technique and literature study. The theory applied in this research is Linguistic Landscape (LL) from Landry and Bourhis (1997)

The research found 404 outdoor signs of Linguistic Landscape in tourism destinations of Gianyar Bali. The findings included into five categorizations, they are (1) nature, (2) culture, (3) village, (4) museum, (5) manmade attraction. The pattern construction of Linguistic Landscape found in those tourism destinations are topdown and bottom-up. The top-down pattern can be found in three categories, they are village, culture and museum. In the other hand, the bottom-up pattern can be found in all categories of LL of tourism destination in Gianyar Bali. Nature and man-made category share equal number of bottom-up pattern and the least is village category. The top-down pattern shows that village category reached the highest percentage number of outdoor signs found among the three categories, and the least showed by culture category.

KEYWORDS: Category, Linguistic Landscape, Tourism Destination, Pattern, Gianyar, Bali

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of research

Linguistic Landscape has been attention to many scholars and researchers to explore how language used in the environment, how words and images are displayed in public spaces. It provides wide and vary opportunities of multidiscipline researches to find out meaning, messages, ideologies, functions, economic purpose, geographical mapping, language policy and other dimensions that are too many too mention. This is line with Puzey's statement. Puzey (2016) positions LL as an interdisciplinary study of the presence of various language issues that interact with other languages in public spaces. LL is a relatively new term in applied linguistics studies, but has been closely intersected with other fields of study, such as sociolinguistics, multilingualism, language policy, cultural geography, semiotics, literature, education, and social psychology. Through language interactions in public spaces, the symbolic construction of a space and the use of language in mediating social and political relations can be traced.

Linguistic Landscape itself is a sub-part of Sociolinguistics that specializes in the study of street names, place names, advertisements, traffic signs, offices, information boards, shop signs and so on, as well as everything related to urban information viewed from a linguistic point of view. Landry and Bourhis (1997:23) state that the Linguistic Landscapes (LL) terminology refers to the visibility and salience of languages in public and commercial signs in a given territory or region. It is proposed that the Linguistic Landscape may serve important informational and symbolic functions as a marker of the relative power and status of the linguistic communities inhabiting the territory"

There two important dimensions of LL as a theoretical framework for analyzing public signs. First, LL is a development of sociolinguistic and ethnolinguistic studies that highlight the use of written language in public spaces or certain specific areas. Second, LL is a multilingual approach that innovatively seeks to examine, study, and describe the linguistic situation or landscape in an area, whether monolingual, bilingual, or multilingual (Artawa, 2020; Mulyawan, 2021).

The universal nature of LL can be found in a various form in a city, sub-urban area; not only it can be found in Indonesia, but also in other parts of the world. The exploration of Linguistic Landscape in Indonesia has been carried out by some linguists. There are ample of studies of LL in Indonesia such as by Syamsurijal (2023) concerning LL in Shopping Center in Makasar, Arneta Iftia Pramadhani et.al (2022) who explore LL in Malang City, Purnawati et.al (2022) explores Linguistic Landscape in heritage area of Gajah Mada Denpasar, Suta Paramarta (2022) discusses Virtual Linguistic Landscape (VLL) in government website of Bali

Province, Puspani et.al (2021) concern with signposts in Nusa Penida island, Artawa and Sartini (2019) discussed LL in Kuta which resulted on the finding of diglossia situation, Mulyawan (2017) finds out LL in tourism destination Kuta Bali and others.

LL dynamics reflect the importance of language in a community. The language used in landscape dynamics is not only aimed at providing information, but can also reflect the power and status of language. The use of English in public places, billboards, traffic signs, offices, information boards, shop signs and so on, as well as every outdoor sign related to urban information becomes a phenomenon that needs to be identified and later mapped. Research of LL in Bali can be considered still small in number compare to other researches of LL that have been carried out outside the island. Therefore, this research tries to give additional information of LL in Bali, it tries to explore LL in tourism destinations in Gianyar regency; a regency which is well known for its art, artists, culture and features the most tourist destinations among other regencies.

The formal definition of a tourism destination can be referred to according to Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, Chapter I General Provisions, Article 1, Paragraph 6, which states as follows.

"A tourism destination area, hereinafter referred to as a Tourism Destination, is a geographical area located in one or more administrative areas in which there are tourist attractions, public facilities, tourism facilities, accessibility, and communities that are interrelated and complement the realization of tourism".

Based on the above definition, several important elements can be found in understanding the concept of a tourism destination, such as (a) a tourism destination is the same as a tourism destination area; (b) a tourism destination is a geographical area in one or more administrative areas; and (c) a tourism destination contains tourism elements that build a unified tourism system, such as tourist attractions, tourism facilities, public facilities, accessibility, and community participation. Thus, the tourism destination in Gianyar Regency in this research refers to its position as a unified geographical and administrative area that is a tourism destination area, including all elements that establish the tourism system within it.

Put fold together, this research tries to reveal the LL dynamics in tourism destinations in particular its mapping or categorization and also analyzing the pattern construction of LL found in those destinations.

1.2 Literary Reviews

There are several studies that concern with Linguistic Landscape in Indonesia and also outside of Indonesia.

Artawa and Sartini (2019), Purnawati (2022), Paramarta (2022), Puspani et.al (2021), Mulyawan (2017) are Indonesian linguists whom Bali based researchers who concern with LL in Bali; Syamsurizal (2023) examines LL in public space of Makasar; Ben Rafael et.al (2023) concerns with LL in Israeli cities; Kasanga (2012) examines LL in Central Phonm Pen.

Artawa and Sartini (2019) focus their research on the Linguistic Landscapes (LLs) of Kuta Village as one of the tourist destinations in Bali. The data are in the forms of photos of outdoor signs taken from the research location, and the data obtained by interviewing a community leader and other informants were analyzed based on the LL theory and then interpreted based on the concept of 'market ideology'. The results of the analysis showed that the languages used in these outdoor signs revealed a diglossia situation. In this context, the Balinese language as a symbol of local ethnic identity is marginalized. The results also showed that Balinese people in the research location tend to choose Indonesian and foreign languages to communicate in everyday life. This can be seen as a sign showing how strong is their desire to have the image, prestige, and power owned by those people who can speak those languages.

Puspani et.al (2021) explored signposts in Nusa Penida, Bali to answer Gorter's idea which says that nowadays monolingual signpost are rarely found. The result of the research presents that most of the signposts in Nusa Penida are presented in more than one language (script) which reflects their desire to serve tourism well or to show hospitality and at the same time to show their loyalty to their identity as Balinese people.

Purnawati et.al (2022) writes about Linguistic Landscape in heritage area of Denpasar, Gajah Mada. The heritage area of Jalan Gajah Mada was originally a trading centre but recently it is starting to be developed into a tourist attraction of Denpasar the heritage city. She applies descriptive qualitative research with observation method to all outdoor signs along Gajah Mada Street and theory of Linguistic Landscape. Her findings show that the language that is mostly used in outdoor signboards in this area is Indonesian, even though the shops are mostly owned by Chinese descendants and several Indian and Arabian descendants. It is also showed that an outdoor signboard can have one, two, three, or even four languages simultaneously. For those outdoor signboards that use three and four languages, the two of them are Indonesian and English. Her findings showed that the implementation of

government policies has not been implemented consistently. The outdoor signboards of government agency names were written exactly following the rules while other outdoor signboards are not.

Pamarta (2022) concerns with Virtual Linguistic Landscape (VLL) to analyze the language contestation in the government website of Bali province. He also explores the actualization of centripetal and centrifugal force through Indonesian, Balinese and foreign languages. His research found that the contestation involves Indonesian as national language and identity of Indonesians, the Balinese language and its script and also English and other languages exist to index the global contact of the government. Further he found that Indonesian represents the centripetal force that unites the regional languages.

Syamsurijal (2023) writes about Linguistics Landscape (LL) in public space of Makassar City shopping center. His research is a qualitative research design and the approach applied was the LL approach by taking Ratu Indah, Panakkukang and Nipah Mall as data sources of his research. The results of his research shows that the form of language use in public spaces in Makassar City shopping centres consists of two forms, top-down and bottom-up, the function of language use in public spaces in Makassar City shopping centres consists of two, informative and symbolic functions, and patterns of language use in public spaces in Makassar City shopping centres consist of two, monolingual and bilingual patterns.

Beside Puspani et.al, Mulyawan (2017) also has rather similar discussion regarding public signs in tourism area. His research location was in Kuta, Bali and his focus was on commercial and non-commercial signs. His research found that majority the signs in that area are using English as the sign's presentation. There were only 22 signs use pure Balinese, 19 use Indonesian but written in Balinese script and 2 signs are written in both Indonesian and Balinese.

Ben Rafael et.al (2006) examines and compares patterns of LL in a variety of homogeneous and mixed Israeli cities and in East Jerusalem. His research focused on the degree of visibility on private and public signs of the three major languages of Israel Hebrew, Arabic and English. It also reveals different LL patterns in Israel's various communities: Hebrew-English signs prevail in Jewish communities; Arabic Hebrew in Israeli-Palestinian communities; Arabic-English in East Jerusalem. The research also analyzed the discrepancies between public and private signs

Kasanga (2012) examines Linguistic Landscape in Central Phnom Pen. He examines the distributional pattern of signs in the linguistic landscape of a neighbourhood in the commercial district of Phnom Pen, Cambodia. His research discusses the developing multilingualism from socio-economic and historical perspectives. He found that the Khmer, the national and official language of Cambodia becomes the prominent language applied in the landscape, followed by English. He declares that the high visibility of English has resulted in the gradual displacement of French in the past decade. Assistance leverage, globalization, gentrification, a generational change in attitudes toward languages, the new policy in education and the complex history of modern Cambodia explain the rapid 'multilingualisation' and the rise of English in the graphic environment and in the socio-economic activities.

1.3 Underlying theories

The main theory of linguistic landscape was firstly proposed by Landry and Bourhis (1997) which was applied by many researchers interested in linguistic landscape study. Landry and Bourhis, (1997: 25) defined linguistic landscape as the language of public road signs, advertising billboards, street names, place names, commercial shop signs, and public signs on government buildings combines to form the linguistic landscape of a given territory, region, or urban agglomeration. Meanwhile, Gorter and Cenoz (2007: 2) added that the study of linguistic landscape focuses on the analysis of written information available on language signs in a specific area.

Landry & Bourhis (1997:25) shows that the strong relation among community, space, and language. It states that the most basic informational function of the linguistic landscape is that it serves as a distinct marker of the geographical territory inhabited by a given language community, [...] inform[ing] in-group and out-group members of the linguistic characteristics, territorial limits, and language boundaries of the region where they have entered. The meaning that can be understood from this statement is that LL has an important function to inform the linguistic status of a community that inhabits a certain area, as well as informing other communities or groups that enter that area that they are in a different geographical area and linguistic landscape. Furthermore, Landry & Bourhis (1997:25) also emphasized that writing in LL is a symbolic marker that shows community relationships with their relative power and status. Thus, LL has two main functions, an informative function and a symbolic function.

Other linguists (Gorter, 2006) defined linguistic landscape as the exact study of language as they appear on the signage, and from the other side of the language portrayal which is extremely important, it connects to identity, cultural globalization, the growth of the English language, and the revitalization of minority languages.

All the writings seen in public commonly deliver specific meaning and also messages. They can be featured as in commercial or non-commercial signs. To differentiate the signs, it represented in ‘top-down’ and ‘bottom up’ classification, Shohamy and Gorter (2009). Top-down terminology is intended for authorities, public bureaucracies, and covers public places, public announcements, and street names, while bottom-up terminology is intended for private parties, individual, social actors, such as shop owners, company signs, advertisement, personal announcement and private companies. For top-down feature usually there are certain concepts or procedures that need to be followed such as rules/instruction as it is instructed from the top (national level) to down (grass-root level). However, this must not be applied when it concerns with bottom-up LL classification. Majority the signs or outdoor signs will have no certain concept or procedures; they usually performed with various creative ideas, type of writings, color and designs.

Ben-Rafael et al. (2006: 10) defined the primary distinction between the two categories as that the top-down is considered to signify a general commitment to the dominant culture, for example, the local language. Whereas, the bottom-up is more flexible since it is produced by individuals to follow recent phenomena. Thus, it can be said that the main difference between top-down, and bottom-up is the actors who issued the sign.

METHOD

This research is field research with observation method and applying image capture and note taking technique. The data collected by finding outdoor signs in tourism destinations in Bali, particularly in Gianyar Regency. The data limited into Indonesian-English text of the outdoor signs, and the outdoor signs not include political pamphlet or unnecessary banners. This regency feature major tourism destinations compare to other regencies of Bali. There are sixty-one (61) tourism destinations in this area (Tourism Office of Bali Province, 2023). The data later being classified and analyzed based on the theory applied. The theory applied for this research is the Linguistic

Landscape theory by Laundry & Bourhouis (1997). The data presented descriptively and supported by static descriptive to give elaboration of the found data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part elucidates the findings of the research and also analyze the findings of the research based on the underlying theories applied. The LL dynamics and its categorization found in the tourism destinations in Gianyar are as follow:

Table 1. Linguistic Landscape categorization of tourism destinations in Gianyar Bali

NO	CATEGORIZATION OF LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE	NUMBER OF OUTDOOR SIGNS	NUMBER OF TOURISM DESTINATIONS IN GIANYAR
1	NATURE	6	20
2	CULTURE	13	12
3	VILLAGE	27	8
4	MUSEUM	23	6
5	MAN-MADE-ATTRACTION	335	15
	TOTAL NUMBER	404	61

The above table shows Linguistic Landscape dynamic found in tourism destination of Gianyar Bali. According to Bali Tourism Office Statistic 2022, there are sixty-one (61) places that included as tourism destination in Gianyar regency. Those tourism destinations are categorized into five LL dynamics, they are: (1) Nature, (2) Culture, (3) Village, (4) Museum, and (5) Man-made attraction. There are twenty (20) places that categorized as Nature. It includes beaches, rice paddy, river valley, cliff temple, natural cave and waterfall. Culture includes temples, and palace and performance stage. Village categorization shows six (6) villages and

two (2) urban villages; the villages are Batubulan, Celuk, Batuan, Bona, Mas, Peliatan and the other two (2) urban villages are Ubud and Gianyar. There are six museums included as tourism destinations in Gianyar, they are Museum Arma, Neka, Puri Lukisan, Rudana, Blanco and Museum Purbakala. Man-made attraction exposes fifteen (15) places such as Bali Bird Park, Reptile Park, Bali Safari Marine Park, Elephant Park and others.

The table also shows that the biggest number of outdoor signs of tourism destinations in Gianyar Bali showed by man made category. There are 335 signs exposed in this category. In the contrary, the least number of outdoor signs displayed can be seen in nature category. There are only six (6) outdoor signs found in those tourism destinations. There is a significant difference in number between nature and man-made category. This finding show fact the local government tends to prioritize man-made attraction LL compare the nature existence and also other categories.

Figure 1 Linguistic Landscape Pattern of Outdoor Signs of Tourism Destination in Gianyar Bali

The above figure shows the Linguistic Landscape pattern of Tourism Destination in Gianyar Bali which represented in static descriptive. According to graphs the bottom-up patterns significantly showed by the red color graphs which can be found in all categories; the culture, village, museum, nature and man-made attraction. The bottom-up terminology is intended for private parties, individual, social actors, such as shop owners, company signs, advertisement, personal announcement and private companies.

Nature and man-made category share equal number of percentages of bottom-up patterns. Unlike the bottom up, the blue graphs that represent the top-down pattern can be seen only in three categories, such as culture, village and museum. There was not found any top-down pattern in nature category.

The three categories show only small number in the usage of outdoor signs in tourism destinations in Gianyar Bali. The highest shown by the village category, the least can be identified in culture category. Culture category involves temples and stage performance in the surrounding area of Gianyar. The temples are Penataran Sasih, Kebo Edan, Gunung Kawi, Mangening, Tirta Empul, Gaduh, Puseh Celagi and Samuan Tiga Temple. The percentage number shown by this category only reach 10 percents out of all outdoor signs found of this research. This finding resonates the fact that there is a lot that need to be improved in the coming year to give better linguistic representation, particularly in culture category because temple visit is one of must visit tourism program in Bali, particularly in Gianyar, not just for local but also for foreigners.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis, this research concludes that there are various dynamic of Linguistic Landscape found in tourism destinations in Gianyar, Bali. The dynamic of the LL categorized into five, they are nature, culture, village, museum and man-made attraction. The pattern of the LL found in this research are top-down and bottom-up pattern. The top down can be seen in three

categories, such as village, culture and museum. In the other hand, the bottom-up pattern includes all categories, they are village, culture, museum, nature and man-made attraction. The highest top-down pattern can be found in village category and the bottom-up pattern can be found equally in man-made attraction.

The findings of this research are expected to be able to use as reference for the local government to put concern in those three categories, and also in nature category. The implementation of providing written information in the open spaces, in particular tourism destination will be beneficial not only for local and foreign tourists who visit but also gives readiness sense for local government, local community to be set as tourism destination. The readiness will give wider impact in national and international realm. Hence, the linguistic landscape should be well concerned and represented.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to extend our gratitude to Udayana University through the Institute of Research and Community Service for giving opportunity and support our research. We also would like to extend our gratitude to English Department students, Agus Winata, Razaya and Yuna who have assisted us with data collection.

REFERENCES

1. Artawa, K., Sartini, N. W. (2018). Linguistic landscapes: A study of human mobility and identity change. *Urban studies: Border and mobility*, 165-172, Routledge.
2. Artawa, K., Mulyawan, I. W. Satyawati, M.S., Erawati, N. K. R. (2020). Balinese in public spaces (A linguistic landscapes study in Kuta Village). *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(7), 6-10. <https://www.jcreview.com/paper.php?slug=balinese-in-public-spaces-alinguistic-landscapes-study-in-kuta-village>
3. Ben-Rafael, E., Shohamy, E., Amara, M.H., Trumper-Hect, N. 2006. Linguistic Landscape as Symbolic Construction of the Public Space: The Case of Israel, *International Journal of Multilingualism*, vol 3(1), pp.7-30, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790710608668383>
4. Cenoz, J. 2009. Towards multilingual education: Basque educational research from an international perspective. *Multilingual Matters*. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781847691941>
5. Cenoz, J., & Gorter, D. 2006. Linguistic landscape and minority languages. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 3(1), 67–80. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790710608668386>
6. Lai, M. L. 2013. The linguistic landscape of Hong Kong after the change of sovereignty. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 10(3), 251–272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2012.708036>
7. Landry, R. & Bourhis, R. Y. 1997. Linguistic landscape and ethnolinguistic vitality: An empirical study. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 16(1), 23–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X970161002>
8. Lanza, E., & Woldemariam, H. 2009. Language policy and globalization in a regional capital of Ethiopia. In E. Shohamy & D. Gorter (Eds.), *Linguistic landscape: Expanding the scenery* (pp. 189–205). Routledge.
9. Reh, M. 2004. Multilingual writing: A reader-oriented typology — with examples from Lira Municipality (Uganda). *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 2004(170), 1–41. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl.2004.2004.170.1>
10. Ross, N. 1997. Signs of international English. *English Today*, 13(2), 29–33. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0266078400009597>
11. Shang, G., & Guo, L. 2017. Linguistic landscape in Singapore: What shop names reveal about Singapore's multilingualism. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 14(2), 183–201. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2016.1218497>
12. Shohamy, E. & Gorter, D. (Eds.). 2008. *Linguistic landscape: Expanding the scenery*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203930960>
13. Gorter, D. Foreword: Signposts in the Linguistic Landscape in C.Helot, M.Barni, R.Janssens, and C.Bagna (eds.), *Linguistic Landscapes, Multilingualism and Social Change*, pp.9-12, Peter Lang
14. Djajasudarma, T. Fatimah. 1993. *Metode Penelitian Linguistik: Ancangan, Metode Penelitian dan Kajian*. Bandung: PT. Eresco.
15. Ferguson, C.A 1971. *Language structure and language use*. Stanford: Stanford University Press
16. Fishman, J. A. 1972 *Sociolinguistics: A Brief Introduction*. Massachusetts: Newbury House Publisher.

17. Halliday, M.A.K and Ruqaiya Hasan.1985 Language, Context and Text: Aspects of Language in a Social Semiotic Perspective. Victoria: Deakin University Press
18. Kasanga, Luanga Adrien. 2012. Mapping the linguistic landscape commercial neighborhood in Central Phnom Pen. Journal of Multilingual and multicultural development, pp.553-567 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2012.683529> Vol 33 (6)
19. Labov, W. The Study of Language in Its Social Context dalam P. P. Gigioli, ed 1972. Language and Social Context. Middlesex: Penguin Books Ltd.
20. Mulyawan, I Wayan 2017. Glocalization of Balinese Language as Outdoor Signes in Desa Adat Kuta, Bali. International Journal of Education Vol 10 (1) pp. 82-87
21. Mulyawan, I. W. (2021). Mulyawan, I. W. (2021). Maintaining and revitalising Balinese language in public space. Indonesia and the Malay World, 49(145), 481–495. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2021.1910356>.
22. Paramarta, I.M.S. 2022. Kontestasi Bahasa Pada Tanda Luar Ruang di Daerah Pariwisata, Sawerigading vol 28 (1), pp.63-79
23. Purnawati, K. W., Artawa, K., & Satyawati, M. S. 2022. Linguistic Landscape of Jalan Gajah Mada Heritage Area in Denpasar City. JURNAL ARBITRER, 9(1), 27. <https://doi.org/10.25077/ar.9.1.27-38.2022>
24. Puspani, I.A.M., Sosiowati, I.G.A.G., Indrawati, N.L.K.M., 2021. Purposes of Writing Signposts: The Case of the Signposts in Nusa Penida Journal of Current Science Research and Review vol 4 (1), pp. 59-69, <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V4-i1-10>
25. Puzey, G. (2016). Renaming as Counter-Hegemony: The Cases of Noreg and Padania. In Names and Naming: People, Places, Perceptions, and Power, Puzey, G.; Kostanski, L (Editor), 244–272. Multilingual Matters
26. Shi, X., Analysis and Translation Strategies of Public Signs from the Perspective of Pragmatics. Learning & Education, vol 9 (2), pp.27, <https://ojs.piscomed.com/index.php/L-E/article/view/1390>
27. President Regulation of Indonesian Republic No. 63 year 2019, (2019). https://jdih.setkab.go.id/PUUdoc/175936/Perpres_Nomor_63_Tahun_2019.pdf
28. Syamsurizal, 2023. The Use of Language in the Public Space Study of Linguistic Landscape at Shopping Center in Makassar City. Hasanuddin University
29. Sumarsono. 2007. Sociolinguistik. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar

Cite this Article: Sang Ayu Isnu Maharani1, Ketut Artawa, Ida Ayu Made Puspani, Ni Ketut Widya Purnawati (2025). Linguistic Landscape of Tourism Destinations in Gianyar, Bali. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(1), 19-25, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i1-03>